

Fringe dispersion and the transverse attitude

This short note addresses an aspect of fringe dispersion, which has perhaps not been considered before. Fringe dispersion uses the 'transverse' coordinate (perpendicular to the scan) to encode the spectral information, at the same time improving fringe contrast and hence angular precision in the along-scan direction. However, the finite size of the field means that the transverse coordinate is not entirely decoupled from the along-scan coordinate. For instance, in order to interpret the phase differences of different stars in the field in terms of angular separations on the sky, it is necessary to know also the transverse positions (or the transverse attitude of the instrument) with sufficient precision. The desired (maximum) ratio of errors in the two coordinates is approximately given by the inverse of the field size in radians, or 50-100.

A single CCD crossing typically gives an accuracy of about 0.2 mas in the scanning direction, so the corresponding requirement in the perpendicular direction is 10-20 mas per image and CCD crossing.

Without fringe dispersion, the size of the image normal to the scan is about 0.15 arcsec. Given that a CCD crossing of a 15 mag star will give some 15,000 electrons, it is reasonable that the location in the transverse direction can be determined to better than 20 mas, provided that pixel height is not a limiting factor (0.15 arcsec is 30 microns at 40 m focal length).

With fringe dispersion the image is spread out at least 15 times more in the transverse direction, or perhaps to 3 arcsec. Its transverse location must however still be determined to 10-20 mas precision. This provokes some interesting questions:

How does one define the image origin in the transverse direction? (Along scan this question does not arise because the images are - or should be - symmetric, so the 'centre' has a natural definition.) In the transverse direction the 'centre' would have to be at a specific wavelength, but how is that determined? The only method I can think of that is independent of the spectral characteristics of the object is to use the separation of the first-order fringes to determine wavelength. Is this accurate enough?

If anyone has made simulations of the transverse image location problem I would be interested to know something about the results.

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